

Clinical Report Phenotype Extraction Pipeline

This repository contains a set of scripts to build an end-to-end pipeline for processing clinical reports, extracting structured information with LLMs, and mapping phenotypes to the Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO).

The main capabilities are:

- OCR + translation of PDF clinical reports.
- Text filtering to keep only patient-relevant information.
- Phenotype extraction using an LLM (via Ollama).
- Mapping extracted phenotypes to HPO terms using embeddings and fuzzy matching.
- Extraction of diagnosis codes from reports using OMIM.
- A higher-level pipeline script to process `.docx` reports end to end.

Repository Structure

```
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├── DataExtractorPipeline.py
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├── PhenotypeExtractor.py
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├── WordTextExtractor.py
├── InfoExtractor.py
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├── utils.py
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├── prompts_and_config/
└── OutputFiles/
```

Requirements

- Python 3.9+
- Ollama installed and running
- Tesseract OCR

Python packages:

```
deep_translator==1.11.4
docx==0.2.4
Flask==3.1.2
fuzzywuzzy==0.18.0
InquirerPy==0.3.4
```

```
json_repair==0.48.0
matplotlib==3.10.8
more_itertools==10.8.0
numpy==2.3.5
ollama==0.6.1
pandas==2.3.3
pdf2image==1.17.0
pronto==2.7.0
psycopg2==2.9.11
PyJWT==2.10.1
pytesseract==0.3.13
python_Levenshtein==0.27.3
Requests==2.32.5
scikit_learn==1.8.0
torch==2.8.0
transformers==4.55.0
```

Starting the LLM Backend

```
./start_ollama.sh
# or
ollama serve
```

In our experiments, we use the `gpt-oss:120b` model, which is available on Ollama Hub and, based on our preliminary tests, performs well for phenotype extraction tasks.

Main Python modules

In the following, we report the main modules that can be used independently or as part of the end-to-end pipeline, and we report their main inputs and outputs.

- **PDFTranslator.py**: Translates and extracts text from PDF clinical reports using OCR.
 - Main inputs:
 - PDF file path
 - Prompt file for file translation (by default `prompts_and_config/translation_prompt.txt`)
 - Main outputs:
 - Translated text file (by default in `OutputFiles/ClinicalReport_TRANSLATED.txt`)
- **PDFTextExtractor.py**: Filters text from PDF files by removing non-patient-related information.
 - Main inputs:
 - Translated text file (output of **PDFTranslator.py**)
 - Main outputs:
 - Filtered text file (by default in `OutputFiles/ClinicalReport_FILTERED.txt`)
- **PhenotypeExtractor.py**: Extracts phenotypes from text using an LLM.
 - Main inputs:

- Text file with clinical report (by default in `OutputFiles/ClinicalReport_FILTERED.txt`)
 - Prompt file for phenotype extraction (by default `prompts_and_config/phenotypes_prompt.txt`)
 - Main outputs:
 - JSON file with extracted phenotypes (by default in `OutputFiles/phenotypes.json`)
- **HPOMapper.py**: Maps extracted phenotypes to HPO terms using embeddings and fuzzy matching.
 - Main inputs:
 - JSON file with extracted phenotypes (output of `PhenotypeExtractor.py`). If not provided, the input file is assumed to be `OutputFiles/phenotypes.json`
 - Main outputs:
 - JSON file with mapped HPO terms (by default in `OutputFiles/phenotypes_with_score.json`)
- **DataExtractorPipeline.py**: High-level pipeline to process `.docx` reports end to end.
 - Main inputs:
 - the path to a `.docx` file or folder containing multiple `.docx` files
 - Main outputs:
 - JSON files with extracted phenotypes and mapped HPO terms (by default in `OutputFiles/`), with name `<case_id>_phenotypes.json`

Typical Workflows

1. PDF → Phenotypes → HPO

This script processes a clinical report in PDF format, extracts phenotypes using an LLM, and maps them to HPO terms.

It requires two arguments: the path to the clinical report PDF and the name of the Ollama model to use.

```
./Pipeline_Script.sh <clinical_report.pdf> <ollama_model>
```

2. DOCX End-to-End Pipeline

This pipeline processes genetic reports in `.docx` format end to end.

It includes text extraction, phenotype extraction, and HPO mapping.

To make it work, it is needed to correctly fill the `prompts_and_config/word_sections.json` file with the sections present in the reports.

```
python DataExtractorPipeline.py -i <file_or_folder> -m <ollama_model>
```

3. Text → Phenotypes → HPO

This pipeline can be used for testing purposes, to extract phenotypes from plain text files and map them to HPO terms.

It requires text to be already in English.

```
python PhenotypeExtractor.py -f <txt_file_path> -m <ollama_model> -p  
<phenotype_prompt_file>  
python HPOMapper.py -f <json_file_path>
```

Note that the phenotype prompt file can be the one we provide in [prompts_and_config/phenotypes_prompt.txt](#) or a custom one.

The JSON file for HPO mapping should be the output of the phenotype extraction step.

4. Individual Scripts

Each script can be run independently (PDFTranslator, PDFTextExtractor, PhenotypeExtractor, HPOMapper, etc.)

Configuration Files

- [prompts_and_config/phenotypes_prompt.txt](#)
- [prompts_and_config/word_sections.json](#)
- [concepts/hpo_concepts_filtered.json](#)
- [concepts/mimTitles.txt](#)

Logging and Output

All intermediate and final outputs are written to [OutputFiles/](#), if no different path is given.